
CHANGE – Data Management Plan

Background

The Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM) leads the Collaboration to Harmonise the Assessment of Next Generation Evidence (CHANGE) project. The project is supported by the Evidence-Based Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC) and the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). The project is funded by EFSA.

The aim of CHANGE is to contribute to regulatory acceptance and implementation of NAM data through identification of system-level interventions that could accelerate the utilisation of effective NAM methods in regulatory risk assessment and the risk management of chemical substances.

We will do this by organising 3 workshops (2024, 2025 and 2026), as well as online events and other activities between the workshops.

The VKM is a scientifically independent, administrative unit within the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH), using the same servers and IT-security systems as the NIPH. These servers and systems are managed by [Norsk Helsenett](#), the national IT-services provider for the central Norwegian public health administration.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is a living document that is updated and expanded as necessary along the lifespan of the CHANGE-project. This version of the plan was created for the organisation of, and follow-up from the 1st workshop, taking place in Oslo 18 – 20 June 2024.

General description of the data

Where does our data come from?

Raw data from the 1st workshop is mainly audio recordings and machine generated transcripts from different interactive sessions (i.e., small group discussions, larger fishbowl discussions). Additionally, notes will be taken, and structured mind maps and blob maps will be prepared jointly.

How do we ensure the quality of the data?

When it comes to the audio recordings and transcripts, the quality and coherence of the data is ensured by using the professional technical services within the VKM's and the Norwegian Institute of Public Health's (NIPH) framework agreement for such services, Berg-Hansen and their subcontractors, as well as resources from the project team.

The subcontractor will set up a recording microphone in each discussion group and record the discussions via a sound mixer and create machine generated transcripts. The audio recordings and the transcripts will be securely transferred to a restricted area on VKM/NIPH's password-protected and access-controlled servers, and only available to specific VKM/NIPH employees from the project team. All recordings and transcripts will be securely deleted from the recording/transcript equipment.

A technician from the subcontractor will be present throughout the workshop to carry out the recordings and the automatic generation of the transcripts. Gisle Solstad (member of the CHANGE project team and employee with the VKM/NIPH) will supervise the process.

Notes and structured mind maps will be handled by the CHANGE project team, ensuring the coherence and quality in line with the planned outcomes future use of the data.

Ethical and legal considerations

Who owns the data?

The data are owned by the NIPH, represented by the VKM.

Do we process personal or sensitive data? Have we carried out a DPIA and/or ethical assessment?

The workshop does not involve the collection or processing of personal data and is therefore exempt from requiring a data protection impact assessment (DPIA) according to the Norwegian legislation. Since no biological materials or information on health will be collected and/or processed in the workshop, the workshop is also exempt from requiring ethics approval.

However, due to the nature of the discussion themes during the workshop, we have assessed and approved measures to increase the confidentiality and anonymisation of the raw data collected.

Measures taken to increase the confidentiality and anonymisation

- Technicians from the service provider are covered by Data Processing Agreement (DPA) between Norsk helsenett, the organisation handling Framework Agreements on behalf on the Norwegian Central Public Health Services, and the service provider and their subcontractors. The same applies for confidentiality.
- Transcripts will be securely transferred together with the audio recording to a restricted area on VKM/NIPH's password-protected and access-controlled servers, and only available to specific VKM/NIPH employees from the project team.
- Audio recordings and transcripts will be securely deleted from the recording equipment after end of each day during the workshop.
- During these interactive formats, participants have the right to flag statements as confidential by clearly stating that they wish for the piece of information to not be recorded in the transcripts (e.g., "The following needs to be off the record.." or "Please consider what I have just said off the record"). If participants realise after an interactive session that they would like to flag a statement that they made as confidential, they can do so by contacting Gisle Solstad (gisle.solstad@vkm.no) and specifying the session and statement. Statements can be flagged as confidential until one week after the workshop (deadline: June 27th 2024, noon).
- Employees of VKM/NIPH who work in the project team will pseudonymise the transcripts, before securely delete the audio recordings and the original transcripts. Notes and mind maps will also be pseudonymised, the original versions will be deleted.
- After the pseudonymising process, the data will be transferred to the VKM/NIPH password protected and access-controlled project area on Microsoft SharePoint.
- However, while we will strive to protect everyone's privacy through this process, the project team do acknowledge it might still be possible to reverse-engineer the institutional identity through contextual cues and indirectly identifiable information. Therefore, the project group will publish overall findings from the research and will do so in a way that does not allow individuals or the organisations that they work for to be identified. The pseudonymised transcripts will not be publicly available but will be made available by request for research projects on a case-by-case basis (requiring a formal ethical approval and a data management plan from the interested party).

- After the project, the data will be stored in VKM/NIPH's password protected and access-controlled data repository.

Documentation

How do we document data so that others can understand the data?

We will ensure the logically and systematically use of metadata to describe where, when, why and how the data were collected. We will ensure a logical organisation of the data throughout the project, as well as logical version controls and folder structure.

Storage and backup

See under ethical and legal consideration for description of where the data is stored.

Members of the project team employed with VKM are responsible for the controlling access to the data:

- Gro Mathisen
- Gisle Solstad

They will also oversee that the data is monitored and controlled according to the VKM/NIPH's data security rules and policies, at the different security levels of data storage throughout the project cycle and after.

Accessibility

Publication of data

The project team will strive to protect everyone's privacy through this process. The pseudonymised transcripts, notes and mind maps will therefore not be publicly available but will be made available by request for research projects on a case-by-case basis (requiring a formal ethical approval and a data management plan from the interested party).

Responsibility

The person responsible for the data management of this project is the Harald Gjein, Director VKM. He has delegated the day-to-day responsibility to the members of the project team employed with VKM:

- Gro Mathisen
- Gisle Solstad

In order to carry out this responsibility, we will use the legal and research administrative resources available to us at the NIPH, as well as the data security and data storage resources available at the NIPH, as well as the [Norsk helsenett](#).